

Effects Of Aronia Fruit On Intestinal Health Probiotic Properties, Benefits Of Its Bioactive Components And Potential Probiotic Effects Of Aronia And Its Interaction With Intestinal Flora On Human Health

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ABSTRACT

Clinical data indicate that these fruits, namely red grapes, are effective in treating several illnesses, including cancer, owing to their significant health benefits. The probiotic effects on the gut and microbiota are crucial for health.

The Aronia fruit was historically used for the first time by Indigenous peoples. The aronia fruit, native to America, was imported and farmed in the Russian Federation in 1900. Since 1950, the fruit has been cultivated commercially in Eastern Europe, particularly in Germany. In 2009, the American Midwest Aronia Fruits Association was founded, and the growing area has expanded annually (Engin and Ark, 2016).

Local populations in North America have used it as a medicinal remedy for millennia. Aronia has been used as dried fruit and as a culinary addition, while its leaves have been desiccated to produce tea. It is abundant in antioxidants. It is the fruit with the highest antioxidant content. It serves as a source of vitamins and minerals.

INTRODUCTION

The Indigenous peoples often included Aronia fruit into their cuisine for its potent effects, using it to bolster illness resistance and sustain immunity throughout the hard winter circumstances. Aronia is favored in cultivation owing to its several benefits, including simplicity of planting, adaptability to diverse soil types, high yields, resilience to cold, heat, and drought, as well as resistance to different diseases and hazardous bacteria. Its significance in human nutrition and its beneficial benefits on numerous ailments have been shown throughout cultivation. Aronia is a novel choice for our nation; it is a fruit that can be cultivated as an intermediate crop and used in both culinary and medicinal applications.

It is also referred to as aronia fruit and black aronia fruit, containing all vitamins except B12 and D. It typically thrives in humid, sunny, or somewhat sunny environments.

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It is impervious to severe cold conditions. They can endure temperatures up to 25°C. Aronia may be grown in every soil type. Aronia plants are averse to high calcareous soils (Tokuşoğlu, 2018).

Studies indicate that Aronia has health advantages. The majority of the health advantages of purple grapes stem from their polyphenol content. A 2015 study in Food Technology and Biotechnology indicates that aronia has the highest polyphenol concentration among 143 plants identified in prior studies. Tolic et al. (2015).

Aronia fruits have shown advantages for several illnesses and human health, including anti-cancer effects. A 2004 research investigated the impact of black currant and gooseberry extracts on colon cancer prevention. The research indicated that although the extracts inhibited tumor or cancer cell proliferation, aronia had the most significant impact (Olsson and Friends, 2004).

Purple grape, Aronia prunifolia (Photinia floribunda), originates from the black grape hybrid but may be classified as a distinct species from the hybrid. A 2009 research indicated that black grape extract aids in mitigating cell damage linked to breast cancer. The research found that aronia extract had preventive attributes in individuals with breast cancer (Kim and Ark, 2016).

AIM

Impact of Aronia Fruit and Its Derivatives on Gastrointestinal Health, Probiotic Attributes, Advantages of Bioactive Compounds. Potential Probiotic Effects of Aronia and Its Interaction with Intestinal Microbiota on Human Health.

METHOD

This study was first prepared by aggregating information from Turkish and international sources, including articles, books, scientific studies, and conferences pertinent to the topic.

FINDINGS

Impact of Aronia on Gut Microbiota Overall

The polyphenols derived from Aronia chokeberries promote the proliferation of gut bacteria. The Aronia grape has properties that promote digestive health. Aronia extracts have antibacterial properties in the small intestine owing to their elevated phenolic content. The gut microbiota significantly influences human health, and current data indicates that its regulation may be achieved by the intake of (poly)phenols. Consumption of red wine (Aronia) by healthy volunteers for a duration of 4 weeks correlates with elevated levels of Bifidobacterium, Bacteroides, and Enterococcus.

The microbial anthocyanin metabolites present in red wine derive from Bifidobacterium, the first metabolite linked to health-enhancing benefits. Aronia has more richness in this regard. It seems to safeguard the gut microbiota via regulation.

Similarly, significant elevations in Bifidobacterium were detected six weeks post-consumption of anthocyanin-rich blueberries (Aronia).

The significance of gut microbiome alteration in relation to the cardiovascular health benefits of polyphenols remains uncertain; however, recent studies indicate that gut microbial metabolism may elucidate the health advantages of polyphenols, which are classified as phenolic compounds.

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BAĞIRSAK MİKROBIYOTASI

dört ana fonksiyonu vardır

(The figure is in Turkish and its explanations are in the text.)

Effects of Aronia on Gut Health Probiotic Properties of Aronia

Aronia extract was shown to influence the expression of genes associated with cholesterol efflux in a dose-dependent way in Caco-2 cells and to facilitate cholesterol efflux in the intestinal lumen. This research indicates that the hypolipidemic effects of the extract may be partially due to enhanced apical excretion of LDL-derived cholesterol and reduced chylomicron production in the gut, where certain isoforms of Sirtuin are significantly involved. Aronia extract was shown to dose-dependently influence the expression of genes related to cholesterol efflux in Caco-2 cells, hence enhancing cholesterol efflux in the intestinal lumen (Özdemir and Özkan, 2020).

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Extensive study has concentrated on aronia fruits and leaves because of their elevated levels of phenolic components, including anthocyanins, flavonoids, and phenolic acids, which enhance their significant antioxidant activity and demonstrate advantageous benefits in mitigating hepatic insulin resistance.

Aronia fruit extracts have in vitro bacteriostatic action against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, as well as antiviral activity against influenza virus A. Research has shown that they impede *Staphylococcus* and *Salmonella* bacteria. Aronia extracts have been shown to have antibacterial properties in the small intestine owing to their elevated phenolic content.

Numerous investigations on different components of the aronia plant have shown its preventive properties against disorders of the digestive system, cardiovascular conditions, and various forms of cancer. The research collected data to assess the antibacterial, antioxidant, and cytotoxic properties of methanolic extracts derived from the fruits and leaves of the aronia plant cultivated under agroecological conditions in Ankara-Gölbaşı. Methanolic extracts were produced from fresh and dried fruits and leaves of the plant, and the antibacterial activity of these extracts against diverse pathogenic microbes was assessed using the microdilution technique, while the antioxidant capacity against DPPH free radicals was evaluated. The cytotoxic impact of the extracts on L929 healthy fibroblast cells was assessed using the MTT test. It was noted that it promotes and safeguards gut flora while also diminishing dangerous bacteria (Cerci et al., 2024).

What are the Probiotic Effect of Aronia on Microbiota and its Properties?

Each organ has microbiota, or flora. The body's microbiota is mostly found in the gastrointestinal system, but it also exists in other regions, including the lungs, oral cavity, skin, genitourinary system, and amniotic fluid.

The terpenes included in Aronia, Chokeberry juice may enhance the overall olfactory character by introducing agreeable fragrant notes. Specifically, terpenes like D-limonene, eucalyptus,

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menthol, linalool, terpinen-4-ol, and α -terpineol found in fermented juice may enhance the olfactory profile of these beverages, even at minimal or trace concentrations, owing to their very low threshold values.

Clinical research suggest that Aronia fruit extract or pure juices provide preventive and therapeutic effects on the microbiota, particularly the digestive system, hence inhibiting the onset of several illnesses due to their probiotic qualities. Microorganisms in these tissues actively contribute to forming and sustaining human physiology and homeostasis, hence being classified as "organs." The gut microbiota is regarded as the second brain due to its abundance of nerve cells and bacteria, and its correlation with chronic disorders. Sonenburg et al. (2018).

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Source Template: Probiotic Effects of Aronia <https://mybiohack.com/blog/black-chokeberry-aronia-melanocarpa-elliott-red-purple>

Aronia melanocarpa is a very abundant source of many chemicals that provide health benefits, particularly polyphenols (proanthocyanidins, anthocyanins, flavonoids, and phenolic acids). These fruits possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, anticancer, antiatherosclerotic, hypotensive, antiplatelet, and antidiabetic effects. Consequently, the use of aronia-derived products is crucial for health prevention and maintenance.

CURRENT SCIENCE

In contemporary society, the rise of infectious illnesses and human exposure to diverse anthropogenic and natural toxic agents necessitates the pursuit of efficient health protection strategies to mitigate exposure to these chemicals, some of which may be hazardous even in little quantities.

In recent years, fruit juices have garnered more attention than dairy products for probiotic administration, since an increasing number of customers are interested in plant-based goods, particularly those adhering to plant-based diets. The primary variables contributing to this shift include lactose intolerance, the elevated cholesterol levels in meat and dairy products, and the allergic reactions associated with milk proteins, which hinder the expansion of dairy or meat-derived probiotics.

In recent years, fruit juices have gained popularity as a medium for probiotic administration via lactic acid fermentation, as shown by several studies. Concerning the lactic acid fermentation of aronia juice, little research efforts have been documented in the literature to far. The lactic acid fermentation of chokeberry juice using four distinct strains of *L. plantarum* yielded an alternative beverage with substantial polyphenol content; nonetheless, no issues regarding its sensory characteristics were noted, which is a significant finding. Furthermore, kefir was used in the fermentation of chokeberry juice, resulting in enhanced polyphenol bioavailability and antioxidant capability.

In this study, the newly identified probiotic strain *Lactobacillus paracasei* SP5, recently isolated from kefir grains, is now designated as *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* (Borowska and Brzóska, 2016).

Aronia, Chokeberry Juice Fermentation Utilization Investigated

- Impact of lactic acid fermentation on the volatile composition of fermented water generated at 4 °C

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Examination of Aronia Chokeberry juice as an appropriate medium for probiotic administration
- Development of a novel food product with probiotic characteristics that can sustain acceptable physicochemical qualities at 4 °C for a duration of 4 weeks. The feasibility of the prospective probiotic strain, residual sugar concentration, volatile compounds, phenolic content, antioxidant activity, and organic acids were assessed after the fermentation of chokeberry juice at 30 °C and 4 °C for a duration of 4 weeks.

Results of Aronia, Chokeberry Juice Fermentation

- Terpenes were detected in fermented chokeberry juice during the entire storage period, with no significant difference in their concentration.
- As reported in previous studies, terpenes can increase the shelf life of products by acting as antimicrobials and antioxidants. Moreover, some terpenes have been found to provide significant health benefits for the consumer, for example α -terpineol can act against *Helicobacter pylori* or even provide anti-Leishmania activity
- The most important result at this point is the beneficial effect that the continuous supply of terpenes can produce, as there is no significant change in their content during storage, which indicates the good quality of the fermented Aronia chokeberry juice.
- From the results of this study, the new *Lactobacillus paracasei* SP5 strain (i) was effective in the lactic acid fermentation of chokeberry juice, which is important for the strengthening and multiplication of probiotics.
- It maintained its viability during fermentation in highly acidic conditions and even at 4 °C for 4 weeks, leading to a product with improved TPC content and antioxidant activity.
- Aronia led to the production of the desired volatile compounds (alcohols and esters) as evidenced by the GC-MS analysis carried out. Aronia, Chokeberry juice appears to be a good substrate for the production of functional beverages with enhanced nutritional value.

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- Due to the high astringency of Aronia chokeberry juice, lactic acid fermentation with a potentially probiotic strain could be a good way to utilize this fruit and direct it to other products with better properties and nutritional value.
- All the above results constitute good first steps to facilitate the commercial development of Aronia chokeberry juice. However, future studies are needed on the organoleptic properties of the product (fermented chokeberry juice) and specific metabolites such as exopolysaccharides and bacteriocins produced by *Lactobacillus paracasei* SP5 strain (Bontsidis and Friends, 2021).

Aronia, Probiotic Effect

- Protects and improves intestinal flora
- Provides a protective barrier against diseases
- Provides high antioxidant support to the body
- Free radicals play a role in inhibiting malignant bacteria and cells
- Thanks to its probiotic effect, it has the effect of repairing the building blocks of the body
- It supports the healthy functioning of the cardiovascular system.
- It has been observed to have an inhibitory effect on cancer types.
- Thanks to its probiotic effect, it highly protects the intestines and microbiota (Bontsidis and Friends, 2021).

Benefits of Aronia's Bioactive Components

Aronias need a chilling time to flower. Due to its late blooming, Aronia is not susceptible to harm from late spring frosts. The investigation on the bioactive qualities of chokeberry fruits assessed titratable acidity and total soluble solids (TSS) content. Ochmian et al. (2012) indicated that TSS levels ranged from 14% to 20%. The titratable acid content, in respect to citric acid, was observed to be between 0.75 and 1.05 g/100 g. Kulling and Rawel (2008) indicated that the pH of aronia fruit varied from 3.3 to 3.7, although Ochmian et al. documented a total acid content of 0.70 g/100 g in terms of malic acid.

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Hudec et al. (2006) indicated that the SSCM value fluctuated between 15% and 24%. This research determined the titratable acid content, expressed as citric acid, to range from 0.1294 to 0.9560 g/100 g. SSCM values ranged from 13.07% to 21.63%, and these findings are somewhat consistent with those of other studies. A notable reduction in titratable acid levels was detected in the Nero and Hugin Aronia fruit cultivars starting from the second year, accompanied by a considerable decline in their soluble solid content (SSC). Nonetheless, no substantial alteration was seen between the two years in the Viking variety. Cold-tolerant Aronia is also capable of withstanding hot and arid environments (Trinklein, 2007). (Trinklein, 2007).

Bio-Chemical Structure of Aronia berries

Aronia berries possess a phenolic composition abundant in dietary fiber, sugars, organic acids, proteins, lipids, minerals (notably zinc and potassium), and particularly vitamin C. Nonetheless, a systematic methodology for examining the substance and amount is absent. Substances present in fruits. This complicates the comparison of data acquired from studies. Such investigations are often conducted using suitable spectroscopic methods or more sophisticated techniques such as HPLC/DAD and HPLC/ESI-MS. The chemical makeup of fruits and the concentrations of these chemicals may fluctuate due to variables like plant growth, fertilization procedures, fruit maturity, harvest timing, habitat conditions, storage methods, and other environmental influences (Özdemir & Özkan).

Benefits of Bioactive Components (Microbiota)

- The growing interest in preventive treatment methods has increased the need for research into natural sources and ingredients that support health.
- Berries (such as *Fragaria vesca*, *Rubus fruticosus*, *Rubus idaeus*, *Ribes nigrum*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Sambucus nigra*) are delicious, low in calories, have antioxidant properties and are rich in fiber and polyphenols (Kulling and Rawel, 2008).

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Berries (red and purple fruits) stand out as potential antioxidants due to their chemical composition and play an important role in the prevention and treatment of many degenerative diseases (Beattie and Friends, 2005).
- Aronia melanocarpa belonging to the Rosaceae family is cultivated for fruit production. Aronia species grow naturally in eastern North America and Canada.
- Aronia plants spread throughout Europe from Germany to Russia in the 1900s. These plants appear as shrubs that can reach 2 to 3 meters in height and bloom between May and June. When ripe, they bear shiny red or black berries (6-13 mm, 0.5-2 g) and are called “Aronia”. Two species are known: Aronia melanocarpa (black Chokeberry) and Aronia arbutifolia (red Chokeberry)
- These fruits are widely used in various parts of Europe for the production of fruit syrups, fruit juices, sweet jams, fruit preserves, extracts and tea.
- Aronia berries are recognized as functional due to their rich chemical content and strong antioxidant activity, and their use and cultivation is increasing worldwide. Thanks to its antioxidant properties, it plays an important role in the prevention and treatment of many chronic and degenerative diseases. Interest in the health effects of anthocyanins is increasing (Bajec and Pickering, 2008).
- Aronia fruits, known for their high anthocyanin content, have been the subject of various studies thanks to these properties, and it has been proven that they offer important protective and beneficial effects on human health thanks to their antioxidant effects and other biological activities (Özdemir and Özkan, 2020).
- Aronia fruits attract attention with their rich content of phenolic compounds such as anthocyanins, flavonols, flavanols, proanthocyanidins and phenolic acids. These fruits create a special astringent feeling in the mouth (concrete, dry and tight effect); this effect is due to the condensed tannins they contain (Sidor et Al., 2019).
- Aronia fruits are used in traditional herbal treatment in addition to being consumed as food due to their rich nutritional content. It is especially preferred in Russia and some Eastern European countries due to its antihypertensive and antiatherosclerotic effects.

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- Many studies have been conducted on aronia, including its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, anticancer, antimutagenic and antibacterial activities, as well as its effect and therapeutic potential in various diseases such as obesity, cardiovascular diseases and autoimmune diseases (Tanaka, 2001).

The Potential Probiotic Effects Of Aronia And Its Interaction With The Intestinal Flora

Probiotics are advantageous bacteria and yeasts that promote the balanced functioning of different bodily systems, including the digestive and integumentary systems, in contrast to pathogenic microorganisms that induce illnesses and infections. Beneficial bacteria, which significantly contribute to neutralizing the pathogenic effects of dangerous bacteria, are naturally present in the body.

Alongside our cells, our body has a system known as the microbiota. All microorganisms in the human body, including bacteria, fungus, viruses, and protozoa, constitute a system, with each individual's microbiome being unique.

Beneficial bacteria included in this microbiome are microorganisms that enhance human health, persist inside internal organs, and are safe for consumption. Due to these qualities, it has no influence on the human body. When their quantities diminish for whatever cause, they may be augmented using supplements. Probiotics have varying effects contingent upon their anatomical location inside the body. These advantageous bacteria are located in the gastrointestinal tract, oral cavity, vagina, urinary tract, dermis, and pulmonary system. Each bacterial colony is accountable for sustaining the equilibrium of its surrounding system. The advantages of probiotics at the intestinal level primarily focus on the optimal functioning of the digestive and immune systems. Beneficial bacteria significantly contribute to the equilibrium of the microbiota (intestinal flora).

Potential Probiotic Effects Of Aronia

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- Regulation of the Body Microbiota
- Positive contribution to the intestinal system
- Benefit to the digestive system
- Strengthening the immune system
- Contributing to the proliferation of beneficial Bacteria
- High probiotic effect against cancer (Bontsidis and Friends, 2021).

Interaction Of Aronia Fruit With Intestinal Flora

Scientific analysis and study have been undertaken on the connection between Aronia fruit and intestinal flora. This research investigated the changes in aronin concentration, total phenols, antioxidant capacity, and microbial composition before to and during ingestion and intestinal fermentation.

The findings indicated that during simulated gastrointestinal digestion, the total phenol content in the intestinal digestion group (ID 2 group) diminished by 53.64%, while the anthocyanin level reduced by 70.45% relative to the original sample. Furthermore, the DPPH inhibition rate was determined to be 32.75%, whereas the T-AOC values of the extracts decreased to 62.89 U/mg.

Anthocyanins include cyanidin-3-arabinoside, cyanidin-3-galactoside, cyanidin-3-xyloside, and cyanidin-3-glucoside. The anthocyanins of Black Aronia (*Aronia melanocarpa* (Michx.) Elliot) have markedly enhanced the relative abundance of *Bacteroides* and stimulated the proliferation of *Bifidobacterium*, *Blautia*, *Faecalibacterium*, *Prevotella*, *Megamonas*, and *Escherichia/Shigella*, among others. It has inhibited the development of.

Positive Effects On The Intestinal Flora

- Protects the intestinal structure and system
- It clears intestinal parasites
- It heals intestinal diseases

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- The intestinal system is regulated by the small and large intestines
- Healing of Wounds in the Intestinal Flora
- It multiplies the positive bacteria in the intestinal tract Strengthened by enzymes in the intestine
- It strengthens the body microbiota through the intestinal tract
- Reduces risks such as bowel cancer
- It destroys harmful microorganisms in the intestinal flora and contributes to its cleaning
- Black aronia (*Aronia melanocarpa* L.) that polyphenols alleviate obesity-induced colon inflammation by regulating the intestinal microbiota and the TLR4/NF- κ B signaling pathway in rats fed a high-fat diet (clinical Finding)

RESULT

Clinical research suggest that Aronia fruit extract or pure fruit juices has preventive and therapeutic effects on the microbiota, particularly in the digestive tract, hence potentially preventing the onset of several illnesses due to their probiotic qualities. Regarding the interaction of Aronia fruit with intestinal flora, various clinical studies have yielded scientific findings indicating that this fruit extract possesses high antioxidant levels and positively influences intestinal flora by enhancing the immune system's support for the microbiota (Min and Friends, October 2024). Anthocyanins provide a beneficial regulatory influence, particularly on the gut microbiota. These research furthermore provide fundamental information for the advancement of anthocyanin-related health and pharmaceutical items (Yu et al., 2021).

It facilitates the normal operation of bodily processes by mitigating inflammation induced by infections. The loss of probiotics, which facilitate many tasks such as digestion and vitamin production, leads to dysfunction inside the body and compromises overall health. The primary roles of probiotics in the body include supporting the immune system, aiding in nutrient digestion, facilitating the synthesis of vitamins, assisting the intestinal epithelial cells,

and inhibiting dangerous bacteria. It infiltrates the body to access the bloodstream and enhances the absorption of administered drugs (Enterogermina, 2024).

LIMITATION

There are limitations in the literature due to the low resources in the research and the limited scientific studies conducted in Turkey and Europe.

NOTIFICATION

Evaluation : It has been evaluated by internal and external consultants.

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ETHICAL DECLARATION

It is a national-based scientific journal aiming to ensure that scientific research and publications are conducted in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and working to achieve this, it has adopted these principles in the field of Health Sciences. The criteria of the Declaration of Helsinki have been taken into consideration.

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